

Conductivity Measurements on Sodium and Zinc Salts and on Bromine in 85% Aqueous Acetic Acid

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In connection with our studies^{1,2} on the bromination of anisole with various added salts, we wanted to know about the extent of dissociation of zinc chloride, zinc bromide, sodium chloride and sodium acetate in 85% aqueous acetic acid as compared to the known values in water. For this purpose, conductivity measurements of the sodium and zinc salts in 85% aqueous acetic acid were carried out. Bromine solutions were also examined for comparison. Conductivity studies are known to provide information about dissociation and ion formation in solution³.

Experimental

Conductivity measurements were made at room temperature ($25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$), using the Wheatstone bridge method⁴ and a cell of Type-I. An audio-oscillator (Physics Instruments Co., Madras-600 032) was used for producing high frequency signals. A telephone receiver was used as a detector.

The cell constant was determined for each experiment with 0.1 N solution of KCl, assuming its specific conductance⁵ to be 0.012856 mhos/cm.

(a) *Specific Conductance of 85% aq. HOAc*

The specific conductance of 85% aq. HOAc was found to be fairly constant: $0.37 (\pm 0.01) \times 10^{-4}$ mhos/cm. However, this value was nearly 10^4 times higher than the specific conductance⁶ of water (5.9×10^{-8} mhos/cm at 25°) and glacial acetic acid (1.12×10^{-8} mhos/cm at 25°). Hence, the specific conductance of 85% aq. HOAc was subtracted from the specific conductance of zinc chloride and other salts studied in this solvent.

(b) *Equivalent Conductance of Sodium Chloride and other Salts*

In Table 1 is given the equivalent conductance for NaCl, NaOAc, ZnCl₂ and ZnBr₂ solutions of various concentrations ($50-4,000 \times 10^{-4} N$) in 85% aq. HOAc. This Table shows that as the concentration of the respective salt is decreased, the equivalent conductance increases (see also Fig. 1).

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TABLE 1
CONDUCTIVITY DATA FOR SODIUM AND ZINC SALTS
Solvent: 85% aq. HOAc Temp.: $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Sl. No.	Conc. (N) $\times 10^4$	Equivalent conductance (mhos cm ²)			
		NaCl	NaOAc	ZnCl ₂	ZnBr ₂
1.	4000	—	—	—	1.12
2.	3000	—	—	—	1.17
3.	2000	9.5	11.3	1.43	1.26
4.	1500	—	12.5	1.46	1.30
5.	1000	13.9	13.5	1.62	1.40
6.	750	14.9	13.1	—	—
7.	500	15.7	15.1	—	1.80
8.	375	16.8	—	—	—
9.	350	—	—	1.61	—
10.	250	17.8	17.3	1.91	—
11.	200	—	—	—	2.55
12.	188	18.8	—	—	—
13.	100	—	17.0	3.30	—
14.	50	22.7	16.9	3.73	—

Fig. 1. Plot of Equivalent Conductivity vs Concentration
▲ NaCl; ● ZnCl₂;
○ NaOAc; △ ZnBr₂

(c) *Equivalent Conductance of Bromine Solutions*

The results of conductivity measurements with 85% aq. acetic acid solutions of bromine are reported in Table 2, which shows that the equivalent conductance of bromine in 85% aq. HOAc is affected by changes in its concentration.

TABLE 2—CONDUCTIVITY DATA FOR BROMINE SOLUTIONS
Solvent: 85% aq. HOAc Temp.: $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Bromine (N) $\times 10^4$	Equivalent conductance (mhos cm ²)
216.4	15.9
104.8	15.2
48.4	16.7
9.76	13.5
5.36	17.5

Discussion

The equivalent conductance at infinite dilution

estimated from Fig 1 are the following : (for 85% aq. HOAc)

Sodium chloride : 23 mhos cm^2 ; Sodium acetate : 18 mhos cm^2 ; Zinc chloride : 4 mhos cm^2 ; Zinc bromide : 4 mhos cm^2 .

The equivalent conductance at 25° and 0.1N concentration of sodium chloride in 85% aq. HOAc and in water⁷ are 14 and 111 mhos cm^2 , respectively. For sodium acetate, the corresponding values are 14 and 73 mhos cm^2 , respectively. From these values, we can conclude that for both sodium chloride and sodium acetate, the dissociation in 85% aq. HOAc is considerably lower than in water.

For zinc chloride, the equivalent conductance at 0.1N concentration in 85% aq. HOAc and in water⁷ are 1.6 and 82 mhos cm^2 , respectively. This shows that zinc chloride is dissociated only to a very small extent in 85% aq. HOAc compared to water. The behaviour of zinc bromide is likely to be similar to that of zinc chloride, because their equivalent conductances in 85% aq. HOAc are comparable (Fig. 1).

In 85% aq. HOAc, the equivalent conductance of bromine solutions (Table 2) is nearly equal to that of sodium chloride and sodium acetate (Table 1). This might be attributed to a slight hydrolysis of bromine in 85% aq. HOAc.

Conclusion

It may be of interest to point out here that the mechanism of the bromination of anisole^{2,8} in 85% aq. HOAc in the presence of added salts such as sodium and zinc salts, only undissociated molecular species of sodium chloride, zinc chloride, etc., are postulated as catalysts. The conductivity data for zinc chloride and zinc bromide discussed above offer support to this aspect of the mechanism of the bromination of anisole in the presence of zinc salts.

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Study on Montmorillonite from Santhal Parganas District in Bihar

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RAJMAHAL hills in Santhal Parganas district of Bihar extending between latitude 24°15' and 25 16' and longitude 87°18' and 87°46' running along river Ganga consist of a flow of basalt of Jurassic age and are said to be primitive mountain composed of black stone¹. Siddique and Bahl² and Satyabrat, Balu and Thomas³ have studied bentonite deposits in India which includes some information regarding the deposits in Bihar. Advancement in mineralogy has led to the academic interest in and economic importance of smectite clay minerals^{4, 5, 6}. We have been interested in our laboratories in the characterisation of the minerals of this area for a variety of reasons¹ and in this paper we are reporting the study of bentonite minerals in the district of Santhal Parganas.

Experimental

Bentonite samples from seven places as coded in Table 1 were taken for investigation. The samples were dried in an air oven for five hours and then powdered to pass through 150 mesh sieve (0.104 mm). The powder was dried in an air oven for 24 hours at 110-120°. The dried powder was cooled in a desiccator and used for all determinations^{2,3} and the properties are reported in Table 1.

All the samples under study were analysed qualitatively and quantitative estimations of some of the constituents were done (wherever feasible) without any pretreatment by standard procedures^{2,7}. The cation exchange capacity was determined by potassium carbonate method⁸ and also by ammonium acetate method⁹. The analytical data and C.E.C. values are recorded in Table 2.

X-ray powder diffractograms for some of the bentonite samples were recorded at the X-ray Laboratory of Indian Institute of Petroleum, Dehradun using X-ray unit X-RD-6 (General Electrical, U.S.A.) while those of the rest of the samples were recorded at the X-ray laboratory of Textile Technology Department of Indian Institute of Technology, New Delhi using Phillips Diffractometer.

I.R. spectra of all the samples were run as KBr pellets on Hilger Watts H 800 i.r. spectrophotometer¹ in the region 400-700 cm^{-1} . The observed i.r. frequencies and X-ray data are reported in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively.

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